

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

O'. Z. Tulanova

**THE BENEFITS OF OLIVE OIL FOR HUMAN HEALTH AND ITS
USE IN COSMETOLOGY**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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